

oMatch: Making Sense Integration Applicable Outside the Ministry of Ontology^{*}

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Abstract

In this paper, we present oMatch, a sense integration method for sensolens-created knowledge hypergraphs based on propositional abstraction. oMatch is designed to match local portions of the graph before aggregation, therefore reducing the hardware requirements to achieve fast sense integration on potentially large hypergraphs. We demonstrate the ability of the method to carry out sense integration on an high-end home cluster with only 12TB of RAM and 5,000 TPU cores for a large multi-hypergraph from the sensolenses of all students in our university, thus demonstrating its ability to support specific communities without the resources deployed by the Ministry of Ontology.

Keywords

sense integration, scale, community graphs, owned truth.

This paper is a work of fiction, written in 2023 and describing research that may be carried out in 2043. For this reason, it includes citations to papers produced in the period 2024-2043, which have not been published (yet); all citations prior to 2024 refer instead to papers already in the literature. Any reference or resemblance to actual events or people or businesses, past, present or future, is entirely coincidental and the product of the author's imagination.

1. Introduction

Since its inception almost a decade ago, the sensolens device has seen a huge increase in adoption, with more than 95% of the world's population over 18 wearing a sensolens for more than 12 hours per day. By using a large variety of high-fidelity sensors, directly plugged onto the wearer's perception channels, and processing those data streams through a full stack of neural models, a sensolens is able to dynamically generate a virtual mental model of the world around the wearer across time: The wearer's personal knowledge hypergraph. This ability to externalize several cognitive functions into the sensolens device has many practical benefits for the wearer. More importantly, the generation and availability of such vast amounts of structured, processable information (i.e. the semantic web of sensolens hypergraphs) are continuing to

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shape our society in complex and subtle ways.

Created on the impulse of the inventor of the sensolens, Mirosoft-NPIDIA¹ and to address the issues raised at the start of the technology, the role of the US Ministry of Ontology (or its equivalent in most democratic countries in the world) is to aggregate knowledge from its citizen into a common shared-truth knowledge hypergraph, relieving in this way individual sensolens wearer from having to validate what has started to be called, using a fashionably retro vocabulary, “the common sense hypergraph”. In practice, all sensolenses are now required by regulation to rely on and carry three hypergraphs: The shared Ministry of Ontology hypergraph, the wearer’s contribution hypergraph, and the wearer’s private hypergraph. The process of dynamically constituting the wearer’s contribution hypergraph in a way that is complementary and yet consistent with the shared hypergraph is out of the scope of this paper, as is the process of deciding which part of the contribution graph is left in the private hypergraph. Although these two aspects of sensolenses relate to active areas of research (see, for example, [1] and [2]), they are described in sufficient detail in the manuals of common sensolenses (e.g. [3]).

In this paper, we are interested in the larger problem associated with updating the Ministry of Ontology’s shared hypergraph, a process known as *sense integration*. This process aims to aggregate propositions from citizen wearers’ contribution hypergraphs in a way that is at the same time sufficiently fast to avoid knowledge out-of-dateness and sufficiently validated so that those aggregations remain suitable as shared truth for all citizens. For this reason, the US Ministry of Ontology, for example, employs a large number of consultants and very large computing resources to compile its weekly update of the shared hypergraph. Despite this, lags have still been experienced in recent years, in some cases with dramatic consequences (see, for example, [4]).

This issue has also attracted a lot of attention in recent weeks due to the growing debate around *owned truth*: the idea that a centrally managed shared truth for all citizens created in an opaque, government-backed process might have damaging societal consequences and that a more transparent and participative alternative should be found. Whether one is in favor of owned truth or not, this debate has been so far fruitless considering that owned truth, as a concept, is currently not technically achievable since only the Ministry of Ontology has access to the resources necessary to carry out sense integration at any significant scale. Opening up the Ministry’s process would therefore only result in showing its inapplicability for even the smallest of communities.

In this paper, we tackle the issue of making sense integration applicable on more modest resources, i.e. commodity clusters of only a few thousand TPU cores. Our method for achieving this relies on two main ideas: First, we use the approach of propositional abstraction as the core technique for sense integration. As described in the next section, propositional abstraction is a process fundamentally different from the ones used currently for sense integration insofar as it relies on the symbolic manipulation of the statements in the sensolens wearer’s hypergraph, in relation to the shared hypergraph. As a result, this method, while not very scalable, has the advantage of being able to aggregate knowledge from potentially small graphs (a few billion hyperedges) with low hardware requirements.

¹Disclaimer: by contractual obligation, the author can only make positive statements about Mirosoft-NPIDIA who are sponsoring this research

Second, to address the issue of the scalability of propositional abstraction, we first apply a multigraph partitioning method to group hyperedges from all the wearers’ hypergraphs into smaller sets that are likely to lead to aggregated, shared knowledge. Here, to ensure that the created partitions are relevant for sense integration, we also rely on the shared graph as a way to group hyperedges not only for being close in the neural space, but also in the semantic space that the shared hypergraph represents. We believe that this, ensuring that the two sides of our method rely on a common ground, the “background knowledge” provided by the shared hypergraph, is key to its performance.

2. Related Work

Very few recent works have attempted to improve the applicability of sense integration in smaller settings than those associated with the creation of the shared graph at the Ministry of Ontology. However, some attempts were made, before the creation of the Ministry and as part of the research that has led to the current process in place, to find methods that could be used with limited resources (see, for example, [5, 6]). However, those methods were only evaluated on downscaled graphs and were found not to be applicable at the more realistic scales with which we are dealing in this paper.

The propositional abstraction technique used here is not new. It has been developed mostly within the group of the author [7] to support intermediary steps in the processing of wearers’ hypergraphs (see [8] for a review of common applications of propositional abstraction). In short, propositional abstraction is a process to suggest additional hyperedges from existing ones in a hypergraph by abstracting the element of existing hyperedges according to the background knowledge represented by a shared graph.² This has enabled, for example, the completion of wearers’ graphs in a way that does not require one to go back to the neural layer of their sensolens and that is, in a related way, less resource consuming. It was, however, found to have two main shortcomings that are addressed here by the use, prior to propositional abstraction, of multigraph partitioning: First, it could only be applied on a single wearer’s graph in relation to a shared graph, and second, it cannot handle the scale associated with the aggregation of a number of different wearers’ graphs.

Multigraph partitioning has recently become a growing topic of interest in the community as a set of approaches to efficiently apply standard hypergraph partitioning methods on multiple hypergraphs [9]. Hypergraph partitioning groups either nodes or hyperedges (depending on the method applied) of a single hypergraph based on the specified metrics to optimize [10]. Multigraph partitioning, on the other hand, takes multiple hypergraphs that are somehow related to each other and groups the nodes or hyperedges of all those graphs into groups of subgraphs of each. In addition to efficiency at extremely large scales, a great difficulty in multigraph partitioning is establishing a criterion for partitioning, ideally a metric, that can be consistently evaluated across the different graphs (see, for example, [11, 12, 13]). Since all the

²We take the opportunity to thank the anonymous reviewer of our previous paper, evidently from an older generation, who remarked that propositional abstraction was related to a process called “Inductive Logic Programming”. We unfortunately could not access the suggested references, as those were published well before the creation of Blockchain arXiv (BarXiv), i.e. in the 1990s.

graphs to partition relate to the same shared hypergraph, we rely on a measure of alignment with the shared hypergraph as a criterion for partitioning.

3. Propositional Abstraction from Multigraph Partitions

Propositional abstraction relies on a shared graph to abstract multiple hyperedges into a common aggregated hyperedge as a candidate for sense integration into a new shared graph. The main idea in this paper is that we can reduce the scale of the task by concentrating on subgraphs of the wearers' hypergraphs that are similarly aligned to the shared graph. This idea leads to a specific approach in the application of multigraph partitioning using common alignment with the shared hypergraph as the criterion for partitioning.

3.1. Multigraph Partitioning through Common Alignment

We rely on a hyperedge-based technique for multigraph partitioning. This means that our goal is to group subsets of the hyperedges of each graph into subgraphs that, together with the (potentially empty) subgraphs of other graphs, will form a multigraph partition. We apply a common approach, which consists of agglomeratingly grouping related hyperedges independently from their origin graph until the desired number of partitions is reached. The central point here is therefore the assessment of the relatedness of hyperedges.

As mentioned above, we use the criterion of common alignment with the shared graph as criterion here. By common alignment, we mean that two hyperedges should be considered strongly related if they: 1- are connected, directly or indirectly, with the same entities and concepts of the shared graph and 2- if they take the same propositional stance in contrast with the shared graph. Although the computation of those two components of our relatedness measure are nontrivial, because of space limitations, we only describe the general principles below.

To check how much two hyperedges connect with the same "region" of the shared graph, we define a distance, which we call SOC (sensolens ontology connectedness), defined broadly as follows:

Definition 1. $SOC(he1, he2, G)$, with $he1$ and $he2$ two hyperedges and G a graph, is a distance measure based on the mean-aggregated, normalised number of hops in the graph G to connect all nodes of $he1$ to all nodes of $he2$. If one of those nodes does not already have a corresponding node in the shared graph, its concept is used instead, adding one hop to the computation. In the unlikely scenario that a node does not yet have a corresponding concept in the shared graph, the node is left out of the computation of the SOC distance.

Measuring the alignment with the shared graph of two hyperedges with respect to their propositional stance is a known difficulty, which can have complex consequences in core hypergraph processing tasks [14]. Since it is used here to decide on partitioning, the impact of the precision of the definition of propositional stance can be less critical. We therefore rely on a relatively simple measure called HS (hierarchical stance), defined in [15], which relies on the position of nodes in the hyperedge and of their concept in the shared graph's concept taxonomy.

Given a hyperedge he and a graph G , $HS(he, G)$ is equal to 1 if he is in complete agreement with G , and to -1 if in complete disagreement. In order to combine it with the distance measure above, we define here nHS as a rescaled HS measure with values between 0 and 1.

Having measures for both our components, we define SHReM (Shared Hypergraph Relatedness Measure) as a simple combination of the two components in the following way:

$$SHReM(he1, he2, G) = \alpha \cdot SOC(he1, he2, G) + \beta \cdot |nHS(he1, G) - nHS(he2, G)|$$

Here, α and β are weights that can be adjusted for both components of SHReM. To simplify, we do not assess below the impact of these weights (which is left for future work) and fix them as $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$.

3.2. Propositional Abstraction on Multigraph Partitions

Having established the approach for multigraph partitioning above, the remainder of the process, which we call oMatch, essentially consists of applying propositional abstraction to each partition individually. To do that, we simply merge all subgraphs in each multigraph partition into a unique graph, making propositional abstraction applicable. This produces candidate aggregated hyperedges for integration which are checked for redundancies and contradictions.

4. Evaluation

To evaluate oMatch, we tested it on the hypergraphs of all the sensolens wearers among the student and staff population of our university, using the weekly shared graph produced by the US Ministry of Ontology. This represents approximately 50,000 hypergraphs of more than 20 billion hyperedges each. While this is far from the scale dealt with for a larger population, it still represents a realistically large set of hypergraphs for a given community, and one that is already out of reach of commodity hardware when applying other sense integration methods. Furthermore, the EU-US Shared Truth Agreement [16] has been in place for a sufficiently long period of time to ensure that the sensorlenses of all wearers in this community have received the update that automates the use of the US shared hypergraph. While relegating the French shared hypergraph to a secondary role is still raising a lot of controversy in French institutions, the practical benefits of ensuring that a common shared graph is available across many nations and citizenships is clearly visible in this research.

A key factor in the performance of our sense integration approach is the number of partitions created through multigraph partitioning. We therefore assess both efficiency-related measures and performance-related measures, varying the number of partitions logarithmically between 100 and 1,000,000.

Figure 1 shows the evolution of the amount of RAM (in GB) and the time (in seconds) required to perform the entire sense integration process on all hypergraphs collected in a high-end “home” cluster with 12TB of RAM and 5,000 TPU cores. As can be seen, unsurprisingly, RAM requirements decrease linearly with the number of partitions, since each partition can be treated separately. In terms of time, the results are less conclusive, as we can see a decrease up to 100,000 partitions, at which point the overhead of dealing with a larger number of partitions

Figure 1: Evolution of memory (RAM) consumption with increase in number of partitions (left) and evolution of computation time with increase in number of partitions (right).

Figure 2: Evolution of the number of generated aggregated hyperedges with increase in number of partitions (left) and evolution of agreement (HS) with increase in number of partitions (right).

takes over. It is worth mentioning, however, that achieving sense integration in this case under 300s, at 100,000 partitions, while still practically limiting, is a significant improvement over previous methods. Unfortunately, we could not consistently compare with those methods as their RAM requirements go beyond the capacity of our test cluster.

In Figure 2, we show how two measures of integration quality evolve with the number of partitions. First, the number of hyperedges aggregated through propositional abstraction gives an indication of the amount of new information potentially integrated into a new (community) shared graph. As can be seen, it remains stable until 100,000 partitions are reached, at which point it decreases rapidly because it does not have enough information in each partition to aggregate. The second measure, agreement between the aggregated hyperedges and the shared graph according to HS, is quite low, probably because the selected community is notoriously prone to contradicting the established truth. The peak in agreement found at 1,000,000 partitions is strongly related to the decrease in the number of hyperedges generated, as seen in the previous chart.

5. Ethical Considerations

The privacy rights of data providers, represented here by the students and staff of our university, are addressed in this research insofar as all students and staff are required at the time of joining to sign an agreement for the use of their sensolens contribution hypergraph by the university for administrative, evaluation, and research purposes. Therefore, all participants duly consented to our use of their data in accordance with the principle of implied consent defined in the European vGDPR.

The author is aware that this research could be used to create out-of-government shared graphs, leading to potential community truth and owned truth practices. Those practices go against current “shared truth” policies [17] and are therefore not condoned by the author. We, however, believe that research into the mechanisms that could lead to such practices is required in the context of the current political debate around owned truth.

Another critical aspect to consider here is that this paper is entirely fake. It is a work of fiction pretending to have been written in 2043 while having been produced in 2023. As such, all of the work described above, the method, the results, and the citations are disconnected from reality and should under no circumstance be taken seriously.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we show a method, oMatch, based on propositional abstraction and multigraph partitioning to enable sense integration at “community-scale” on commodity hardware. We show that this method makes the task feasible and could have a significant impact on research and society. Through future improvements, we hope to be able to achieve sense-integration directly on the sensolens for small groups and families. Also, here we only evaluated our method based on the US shared graph. Understanding how the results obtained are affected when using different shared graphs is an interesting direction. It is in fact a limitation of the approach that all the wearers’ hypergraphs have to refer to the same shared graph for sense integration to be feasible. We are currently researching ways to overcome this limitation.

References

- [1] D. Caroti, L. Trefort, Nn2hg v13.4: A new evolution in neural to knowledge transfer, Sensolens Communications 13 (2042).
- [2] L. Tratifloute, GPT32, C. Volgenite, Dealing with edge cases in hyperedge segregation, W3CIEEE Transactions on Privacy and transparency 23 (2041).
- [3] Mirosoft-NPIDIA, Sensolens 156 manual, 2042.
- [4] J. Miller, E. Williams, On the importance of hypergraph updates at the time of the cordyceps pandemic, in: Proceedings of the 12th international colloquium on societal technology in health policies, 2039.
- [5] A. Inn, R. Land, Aggregating hyperedges through context-free hypergrammars, in: Proceedings of ACmL (association for computational metalingistic), 2037.

- [6] R. McMillardise, Neurofca-based sense integration, in: Proceedings of the Euroasian Semantic Web Conference, ESWC, 2035.
- [7] E. Jay, J. Bannay, M. d'Aquin, Propositional abstraction: Building knowledge from hypergraphs, *Semantic Web Semantics Journal* 28 (2038).
- [8] M. d'Aquin, L. Nair, A survey of applications of propositional abstraction from the point of view of efficiency, *Knowledge engineering review* 45 (2041).
- [9] L. Bobcat, V. Javascript, Multigraph partitioning: Methods and applications, *Journal of hypergraph processing* 6 (2040).
- [10] J. Wick, L. Bobcat, Metrics definition for hypergraph partitioning, *Communications of the PACM (pan-american association for computing and machinery)* 8 (2033).
- [11] L. Vellam, Revised entropy: A universal metric for multigraph partitioning?, in: Proceedings of the PACM conference on distributed hypergraph management, 2039.
- [12] L. Vellam, One size does not fit all, or why there cannot be a universal metric for multigraph partitioning, in: Proceedings of the PACM conference on distributed hypergraph management, 2040.
- [13] L. Vellam, The light at the end of the tunnel: Some metrics are better than others in multigraph partitioning, in: Proceedings of the PACM conference on distributed hypergraph management, 2041.
- [14] O. Villanelle, E. Polastri, C. K. Konstantine, Impact of stance-related measures on hypergraph distillation, in: Proceedings of the international conference on neuro-symbolic computation, 2035.
- [15] P. Cunk, Cumulative hierarchical stance alignment and its applications, in: Proceedings of the international conference on neuro-symbolic computation, 2032.
- [16] E.-U. committee for the harmonisation of the truth, Eu-us shared truth agreement: One truth to rule them all, 2042.
- [17] U. K. D. Committee, The international shared truth act: Do not think different, 2038.